

A Renewed Numerical Exploration of the Triviality of the Quartic Scalar Field Theories

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Abstract

We explore the triviality properties of the quantum field theory of a scalar field with a single real component and a quartic potential term in the action. The scalar quantum field theories are important because they constitute the scalar sector of the standard model of particle physics. The single scalar field left over after spontaneous symmetry breaking has been implemented in that model is known as the Higgs field. The triviality of the theory means that, although its ensemble is not Gaussian, all its expectation values are identical to those that can be obtained from a Gaussian theory, with appropriately chosen parameters.

We present here numerical results with high-quality statistics, that strongly support the conclusion that the theory is in fact trivial. We measure the dimensionless renormalized mass parameter of the scalar field theory in several different ways, some of which would be valid only if the theory was in fact trivial. One of these measurements has a global character over the whole lattice, since it is done in momentum space, and is in fact the usual way to measure this parameter. The other five measurements are done in position space and have a local character, being valid on single lattice sites, single lattice links or single diagonals of plaquettes.

The expressions for the local observables used for these measurements are derived with the use of the Gaussian ensemble of a free theory, and therefore can be valid only if the quartic theory is in fact trivial. We will show that not only there is strong evidence of triviality, but that in some cases this triviality seems to be in force already on finite lattices, instead of only in the continuum limit.

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1 Introduction

The problem of the triviality of the polynomial scalar field theories is a longstanding one. The basic numerical facts associated to this have been known for a long time [1]. There is still no complete analytical proof of triviality in the particularly important case of four-dimensional spacetime, but a rather involved proof for five or more dimensions was published more than four decades ago, in 1981 [2, 3]. Since that time there has constantly been some amount of confusion about this issue, so that an effort to analyze and describe the situation in simpler and clearer terms, even in the absence of a complete proof in the most relevant case, seems plainly justified. In this paper the scalar field theory will be defined in a mathematically precise fashion using a discrete representation on what is known as an *Euclidean lattice*. The continuum theory in Euclidean space is to be obtained as a limit from this discrete Euclidean construction, after which a Wick rotation is executed, leading to the corresponding continuum theory in Minkowski spacetime.

In this paper we will examine under a new light some aspects of a well-known family of scalar theories in the general subject of lattice quantum field theory, known as the $\lambda\varphi^4$ *polynomial scalar theories*. This is a family of quartic non-linear theories of scalar fields that has great fundamental importance due to the fact that it plays a vital role in the structure of the so-called *standard model of particle physics*. The scalar sector of that standard model contains a scalar field theory of this family, for a doublet of complex scalar fields, that is essential to implement the process of *spontaneous symmetry breaking* which is at the very core of the structure of that standard model. Once the process of symmetry breaking has been completed, a single real scalar field component is left over, with its dynamics given by an action that contains a quartic term. This remaining uncharged massive scalar field is known as the Higgs field.

Here we will examine the quantum dynamics of this single-component scalar field, which has a non-quadratic action that contains a potential term given by a quartic polynomial on the field. By construction this theory displays the phenomenon of spontaneous symmetry breaking. We will show some very interesting facts about the theory, facts that are related to the well-known issue that is described as the *triviality* of the quartic scalar theories, in particular in the case of four spacetime dimensions. This property is better analyzed in terms of the dimensionless lattice fields, rather than in terms of the corresponding dimensionfull fields in the continuum, as is sometimes done. This is so because the two-point function of the dimensionless lattice fields can be properly normalized as a standard statistical correlation function, equal to one at the origin, while the two-point function of the corresponding dimensionfull fields in the continuum is a Green's function, which is singular at the origin. A more detailed discussion of this can be found in Appendix A.

It is important to note that this triviality property has no direct bearing on the role that the scalar theories play as part of the standard model. Sometimes opinions are expressed to the effect that this scalar theory cannot be trivial because this would prevent it from having the effect that it must have within the structure of the standard model. However, this is simply not true, since the trivial scalar theory is perfectly capable of generating a finite and non-zero vacuum expectation value of the field and a finite and non-zero renormalized mass, which are the requirements for the role that the scalar theory plays in the standard model. Such opinions are usually associated with what can be characterized as perturbative thinking about the scalar theory, but one should not attempt to draw fundamental structural conclusions from the perturbative series of this theory, since it is a completely divergent series. A simple proof of this fact, based on the well-known facts about power series established in the theory of analytic functions, can be found in Appendix B.

This paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 we review the quartic scalar theory; in Section 3 we introduce the local observables for the renormalized mass parameter; in Section 4 we describe the computer program used in the numerical exploration; in Section 5 we present the numerical results; and in Section 6 we present our conclusions.

2 Review of the Quartic Scalar Theory on the Lattice

Here we will give the definition and describe the main structural properties of the theory, in order to establish the notation and the basic mathematical facts about it. If we are to make any meaningful and precise statements about any theory, it is imperative that we start from a precise mathematical *definition* of that theory. We will use as the very definition of any given quantum field theory its realization on a discrete Euclidean lattice. In this constructive definition a discrete version of the theory is set up on finite lattices in Euclidean space, in a way which is valid for arbitrarily large values of the size of the lattice. The corresponding theory in the Minkowski continuum is obtained when we make the lattice infinitely large and its mesh infinitely fine, and execute a *Wick rotation* from the resulting Euclidean space to the corresponding Minkowski spacetime.

2.1 Definition of the Theory

In order to define the theory and establish the notation, we will consider a discrete Cartesian lattice with N sites in each one of d spacetime directions, hence with a total of N^d sites and dN^d links between neighboring sites. Roughly speaking, the lattice is a discrete representation of spacetime. If the components of the d -vector \vec{n} are the d discrete integer coordinates of the lattice sites in d dimensions, then the lattice field $\varphi = \varphi(\vec{n})$ is defined as a real function of these discrete coordinates, where

$$\vec{n} = (n_1, \dots, n_d), \quad (1)$$

$$n_\mu = 1, \dots, N, \quad (2)$$

$$\mu = 1, \dots, d, \quad (3)$$

where $\varphi(\vec{n})$ is a single-component real scalar field, which on the lattice formalism is always a dimensionless quantity. The relevant geometrical elements of the lattice itself are its sites \vec{n} , its links ℓ_μ between neighboring sites along the Cartesian direction μ , and its *plaquettes*. By definition the lattice consists of N^d sites, and of dN^d links between neighboring sites. We assume that periodic boundary conditions are used on the lattice, meaning that along any given direction μ the site $n_\mu = N + 1$ is identified with the site $n_\mu = 1$, and that the site $n_\mu = 0$ is identified with the site $n_\mu = N$. Given a site \vec{n} and a direction μ , the link ℓ_μ simply connects the site \vec{n} to its neighboring site $\vec{n} + 1_\mu$ in that direction, and is the natural locus for the finite difference of the two values of the field at either site. Here 1_μ represents the link from the site \vec{n} to its next neighbor in the positive direction μ , going from a given value of n_μ to the value $n_\mu + 1$.

The plaquettes are two-dimensional objects constructed as follows. One starts at a given site \vec{n} and considers two positive directions departing from it, say μ and ν . The plaquette is the square generated by the two links ℓ_μ and ℓ_ν . Since there are $d!/[2!(d-2)!]$ ways to choose the two positive directions from a given site, it is clear that there are $d(d-1)N^d/2$ plaquettes in an N -lattice in d dimensions. If we consider the diagonals of plaquettes, since there are two diagonals per plaquette, it is clear that the total number of such diagonals on the N -lattice in d dimensions is given by $d(d-1)N^d$. Note that these diagonals are necessary

to help upgrade the Cartesian lattice to a *simplicial complex*, over which a definite *metric geometry* can be unequivocally defined. Therefore it is important to be able to determine the lengths of these diagonals, as well as the lengths of the links.

The Euclidean action functional defining the scalar field theory on the lattice is given in this d -dimensional discrete *position space* by

$$S_N[\varphi] = \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\Delta_\mu \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 + \frac{\alpha}{2} \varphi^2(\vec{n}) + \frac{\lambda}{4} \varphi^4(\vec{n}) \right\}, \quad (4)$$

where the sum over \vec{n} runs over all N^d lattice sites, so that it can be expressed as a d -dimensional multiple sum,

$$\sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \equiv \sum_{n_1=1}^N \dots \sum_{n_d=1}^N, \quad (5)$$

and where the lattice squared mass parameter α is a dimensionless real parameter, while the lattice coupling constant λ is a dimensionless positive real parameter. The operator Δ_μ represents the finite difference of the fields across the lattice link starting at the site \vec{n} in the positive direction μ . Note that α can be negative so long as λ is strictly positive, thus ensuring the energetic stability of the theory or, in quantum terminology, the existence of its ground state. These stability constraints will be discussed in more detail in the subsequent Subsection 2.2. If λ is zero then α has to be positive, and in this case our theory reduces to the free quantum field theory of the single real scalar field $\varphi(\vec{n})$. If we introduce a lattice spacing a with physical dimensions of length it is not difficult to show that for $\alpha \geq 0$ the expression shown in Equation (4) tends to the usual classical expression for the action of this theory in the *continuum limit*, within a finite cubic box in d dimensions,

$$S[\phi] = \int_V d^d x \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu=1}^d [\partial_\mu \phi(\vec{x})]^2 + \frac{m^2}{2} \phi^2(\vec{x}) + \frac{\Lambda}{4} \phi^4(\vec{x}) \right\}, \quad (6)$$

where we introduced, still on finite lattices, the dimensionfull quantities given by the squared mass $m^2 = \alpha/a^2$, the dimensionfull coupling constant $\Lambda = a^{d-4}\lambda$, and the dimensionfull field $\phi(\vec{x}) = a^{(2-d)/2}\varphi(\vec{n})$, where $\vec{x} = a\vec{n}$ are now dimensionfull coordinates on the lattice, so that the minimum possible variation of a coordinate is $dx^\mu = a$, the d -dimensional integration element is $d^d x = a^d$, the lattice length is $L = Na$ and the lattice volume is $V = L^d$. After that we take the continuum limit, in which $N \rightarrow \infty$ and $a \rightarrow 0$, in such a way that the lattice length $L = Na$ remains constant, under some auxiliary conditions involving the dimensionless parameters α and λ of the theory.

The observable quantities of the quantum field theory are the average values of functionals of the field on the statistical distribution of field configurations, also known as an *ensemble*, defined by the exponential of minus the action. These are called *expectation values*, and given an arbitrary *observable* $\mathcal{O}[\varphi]$, which in general is some functional of the field, its expectation value is defined as the ratio of multiple integrals

$$\langle \mathcal{O} \rangle_N = \frac{\int [d\varphi]_N e^{-S_N[\varphi]} \mathcal{O}[\varphi]}{\int [d\varphi]_N e^{-S_N[\varphi]}}, \quad (7)$$

where the integrals indicated are *functional integrals*, that is, sums over the set of all possible field configurations $\varphi(\vec{n})$ on the lattice. On a finite N -lattice in d dimensions they can be written as multiple integrals in a real space of dimension N^d , with the measure

$$[d\varphi]_N = \prod_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} d\varphi(\vec{n}), \quad (8)$$

where the product over \vec{n} runs over all N^d lattice sites, so that it can be expressed as a d -dimensional multiple product,

$$\prod_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \equiv \prod_{n_1=1}^N \dots \prod_{n_d=1}^N. \quad (9)$$

The integrals over $\varphi(\vec{n})$ at each site \vec{n} , shown in Equation (7), are taken from $\varphi(\vec{n}) \rightarrow -\infty$ to $\varphi(\vec{n}) \rightarrow \infty$. In the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit the integrals in Equation (7) become infinite-dimensional integrals, also known as functional integrals in the continuum.

Some of the most important expectation values of the theory are defined in *momentum space*, so let us introduce the representation of the theory in that space. The field $\varphi(\vec{n})$, defined at first in position space, can also be represented in momentum space, in the case of the use of periodic boundary conditions on the lattice, by its *Fourier components* $\tilde{\varphi}$, also known as the coefficients of the expansion of the field in lattice *modes*. If $\vec{\kappa}$ are the discrete integer momentum coordinates of these modes on the *conjugate lattice* in momentum space, then the Fourier components $\tilde{\varphi} = \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})$ are defined as complex functions of these modes, where

$$\vec{\kappa} = (\kappa_1, \dots, \kappa_d), \quad (10)$$

$$\kappa_\mu = \kappa_{\min}, \dots, \kappa_{\max}, \quad (11)$$

$$\mu = 1, \dots, d, \quad (12)$$

and where the extremes of the discrete momentum-space coordinates κ_μ are given by

$$\kappa_{\min} = \begin{cases} -\frac{N-1}{2} & \text{for odd } N, \\ -\frac{N}{2} + 1 & \text{for even } N, \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$\kappa_{\max} = \begin{cases} \frac{N-1}{2} & \text{for odd } N, \\ \frac{N}{2} & \text{for even } N. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

The conjugate lattice has the same geometrical structure of the original lattice, being Cartesian with N points along each one of d independent directions, but which represent now modes rather than sites. In this paper we will use only even values of N , because for algorithmic reasons this is the most important case for the numerical simulations, due to the use of periodic boundary conditions. The finite *Fourier transformation* and its inverse, between these two representations of the field, are exact relations given by

$$\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa}) = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N}\vec{\kappa}\cdot\vec{n}} \varphi(\vec{n}), \quad (15)$$

$$\varphi(\vec{n}) = \sum_{\vec{\kappa}}^{N^d} e^{-i\frac{2\pi}{N}\vec{\kappa}\cdot\vec{n}} \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa}), \quad (16)$$

where the sum over $\vec{\kappa}$ runs over all N^d lattice modes, so that it can be expressed as a d -dimensional multiple sum,

$$\sum_{\vec{\kappa}}^{N^d} \equiv \sum_{\kappa_1=\kappa_{\min}}^{\kappa_{\max}} \cdots \sum_{\kappa_d=\kappa_{\min}}^{\kappa_{\max}}, \quad (17)$$

and where the set of complex exponentials shown in these transformation formulas constitutes a *complete and orthogonal basis* for the representation of arbitrary functions on the lattice, known as the *Fourier basis*. The first expression, in Equation (15) above, defines the Fourier components of the field, and the second expression, in Equation (16) above, can be interpreted as the decomposition of the field in lattice modes. Note that, since $\varphi(\vec{n})$ is real, from Equation (15) it follows that the Fourier components satisfy the constraints

$$\tilde{\varphi}^*(\vec{\kappa}) = \tilde{\varphi}(-\vec{\kappa}). \quad (18)$$

Modes $\vec{\kappa}$ with all components equal to either 0 or $N/2$ are *real modes*, since in these cases the complex exponential functions representing the modes are real functions, and hence the Fourier components are also real. For even N there are 2^d real modes, which are at the vertices of a d -dimensional cube within the conjugate lattice in momentum space, of extent $N/2$ in each direction, going from the *zero mode* $(0, \dots, 0)$ to the maximal mode $(N/2, \dots, N/2)$. For odd N there is a single real mode, the zero mode $\vec{\kappa} = \vec{0}$. Note that from Equation (15) it follows that the coefficient of the zero mode $\tilde{\varphi}_0 = \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{0})$ is a full-lattice *block variable*, that is, the average of the field over the whole lattice,

$$\tilde{\varphi}_0 = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{n}}^{N^d} \varphi(\vec{n}). \quad (19)$$

This real quantity will be instrumental in the determination of the state of symmetry breaking of the quartic polynomial theory. The observable $\langle \tilde{\varphi}_0^2 \rangle$ or, more precisely, the corresponding observable formed by the difference of expectation values

$$\sigma_0^2 = \langle \tilde{\varphi}_0^2 \rangle - \langle \tilde{\varphi}_0 \rangle^2, \quad (20)$$

which is the squared width of the distribution of values of $\tilde{\varphi}_0$, can be used as an *order parameter* for the two phases of the theory, since for large N it tends to zero in the *symmetric phase*, and remains different from zero in the *broken-symmetric phase*. Although the symmetry breaking mechanism only becomes exact in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit, this observable can be used to determine approximately the location of the phase transition in the (α, λ) parameter plane, even on finite lattices. It is noteworthy that the dimensionless *renormalized mass parameter* α_R , to be discussed in what follows, can also be used for this purpose. On finite lattices the direction of symmetry breaking tends to drift (in our case here to flip sign), in such a way that the expectation value $\langle \tilde{\varphi}_0 \rangle$ is averaged out to zero during the drift. This drift only ceases completely in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit.

In the same way, due to this drift and consequent averaging out, the expectation value $v_R = \langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle$ of the field, which in the continuum limit is different from zero only in the broken-symmetric phase, is always zero on finite lattices, in either phase, and hence cannot be used as the order parameter. In order to have $v_R \neq 0$ on finite lattices it is necessary

to break the symmetry by hand, by either using *fixed boundary conditions* oriented in a predetermined way, or including in the theory an *external source* $j(\vec{n})$ with a predetermined orientation, which can be done by adding the term $j(\vec{n})\varphi(\vec{n})$ to the summand of the action shown in Equation (4). Note that the introduction of such an external source would cause $v_R(\vec{n})$ to depend on position, unless $j(\vec{n})$ was actually constant over the lattice.

The action of the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory shown in Equation (4) can be written in terms of $\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})$, as $S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]$, but its form in this representation is neither simple nor particularly useful. By transforming the fields to momentum space we may write the expectation value, in terms of the Fourier transforms of the fields, as

$$\langle \mathcal{O} \rangle_N = \frac{\int [d\tilde{\varphi}]_N e^{-S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]} \mathcal{O}[\tilde{\varphi}]}{\int [d\tilde{\varphi}]_N e^{-S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]}} \tag{21}$$

where the measure is now given *symbolically* by

$$[d\tilde{\varphi}]_N = \prod_{\vec{k}}^{N^d} d\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k}), \tag{22}$$

where for a more precise description $d\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})$ should be replaced by $d\Re[\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})]d\Im[\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})]$, and where the values of \vec{k} and the real and imaginary parts of $\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})$ have to be selected so as to neither under-count nor over-count the N^d independent field variables, that is, they must take into account the constraints given in Equation (18) and the fact that some modes are real and thus have no imaginary parts. The most fundamental expectation value in the theory is that of the *two-point function* in momentum space, also known as the *propagator*, which is defined as

$$\left\langle |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})|^2 \right\rangle_N = \frac{\int [d\tilde{\varphi}]_N e^{-S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]} |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})|^2}{\int [d\tilde{\varphi}]_N e^{-S_N[\tilde{\varphi}]}}. \tag{23}$$

This observable defines the important physical quantity that is the renormalized dimensionless squared mass parameter α_R of the theory. This parameter is related to the *correlation length* of the field on the lattice. In terms of the dimensionfull *renormalized mass* m_R it is given by $\alpha_R = m_R^2 a^2$, so that finite values of m_R in the $N \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ continuum limit correspond to $\alpha_R \rightarrow 0$. This condition implies that all continuum limits converge to the critical curve of the theory, as will be discussed in detail in the subsequent Subsection 2.3. The observable parameter α_R can be defined as the position of the single pole of this momentum-space two-point function, when it is written in the Minkowski spacetime by means of a Wick rotation. The ratios of high-dimensional integrals that define the expectation values can be calculated efficiently and with good precision by stochastic methods known as *Monte Carlo simulations*, or *stochastic simulations*. Since there are no known exact solutions of these non-linear theories, we will have to use these numerical methods in order to calculate physical quantities.

2.2 Stability Constraints

Examining the action $S_N[\varphi]$ given in Equation (4) we now observe that, for any finite value of N , in order for the integrals over each degree of freedom $\varphi(\vec{n})$ to exist and be finite,

and hence for the Euclidean ensemble defined in Equations (7) and (21) above to be well-defined, we need to have one of the following two conditions hold: either $\lambda > 0$ with any real value of α , or $\lambda = 0$ with $\alpha > 0$. This corresponds to the condition that $S_N[\varphi]$ must have a lower bound.

In any case, the condition $\lambda < 0$ implies that the integrals do not exist, because in this case $S_N[\varphi]$ has no lower bound, as one can see by considering arbitrarily large constant field configurations, and therefore the factor $\exp(-S_N[\varphi])$ in the integrands diverges very fast to $+\infty$ at the two ends of the integration interval, that is, both for $\varphi(\vec{n}) \rightarrow -\infty$ and for $\varphi(\vec{n}) \rightarrow \infty$, so that the integrals do not exist. This is true on each finite N -lattice, and therefore it is also true in any $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit. In terms of the Minkowski theory, this condition is translated as the fact that the Hamiltonian of the theory has no lower bound, and that therefore there is no ground state of the quantum theory.

Note that this argument implies that for $\lambda < 0$ neither the classical theory nor the quantum theory exist, for any and all finite values of N , so that this limitation on the possible values of λ is *not* only a consequence of the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit. If the limitation is violated, then the theory fails to exist on each and every one of the finite- N lattices, all the way to the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit.

This fundamental limitation on the values of λ also determines the behavior of the perturbative expansion in this theory. The definition of the observables of the theory given in Equation (7) implies that, given any observable \mathcal{O}_N , and so long as the theory exists at all, its expectation value is a function of the real parameters α and λ of the theory. If there is a perturbative series for this observable, developed around the exactly solvable case of the free theory for $\lambda = 0$, then it must be given by

$$\langle \mathcal{O}_N \rangle (\alpha, \lambda) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n(\alpha) \lambda^n, \quad (24)$$

which is a real power series on λ , developed around the reference point $\lambda = 0$. The possible usefulness of this series comes from the fact that in principle the coefficients $a_n(\alpha)$ can be calculated exactly by analytical means, since they are to be calculated for $\lambda = 0$, and therefore are within the confines of the free theory, where all observables can be calculated exactly, and where every such calculation reduces to the calculation of multiple Gaussian integrals. However, ultimately this series turns out not to be useful, because it can be shown that the series is divergent at all points, except for its reference point $\lambda = 0$. A simple proof of this fact can be found in Appendix B.

2.3 Fundamental Properties

We must now describe the phenomenology of the lattice theory, in particular with respect to the mechanism of the continuum limit and to the mechanism of symmetry breaking, which are related to each other. Here we must point out that the actions shown in Equations (4) and (6) are invariant by an $O(1)$ discrete reflection symmetry, in which we flip the signs of the fields. Both mechanisms are also closely related to the *critical behavior* of the lattice theory in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit, if we interpret it as a statistical model of a set of random variables $\varphi(\vec{n})$. The other crucially important property of the theory is that of the so-called triviality, which we will also describe in the subsequent Subsection 2.4. The *critical diagram* of the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory can be found in Figure 1. This is a qualitative diagram in the space of the parameters of the theory, in our case here the (α, λ) parameter plane. The qualitative aspects of the diagram are the same for any dimension $d \geq 3$, including the important case $d = 4$. Some aspects of the diagram are over-emphasized for visualization purposes. The

Figure 1: The critical diagram of the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory, showing the unstable region, the symmetric region, the broken-symmetric region and the critical curve separating these last two. Flows representing possible continuum limits, from each one of the two phases of the theory, are also shown. For simplicity, the parameters (r, θ) seen here will be used instead of (α, λ) in the simulations.

alternative parameters r and θ , that will be used instead of α and λ in the numerical work, are defined to be such that

$$\alpha = -r \cos(\theta), \quad (25)$$

$$\lambda = r \sin(\theta). \quad (26)$$

The critical behavior of the theory can be well illustrated by varying θ at constant r . The diagram consists of three regions. In the region below the α axis the theory does not exist at all, since in this region, where $\lambda < 0$, it has no stable ground state, given that $S_N[\varphi]$ has no lower bound there. We call that one the *unstable or forbidden* region. The strictly negative part of the α axis is part of this region, since in this negative semi-axis we have $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha < 0$, and once more the theory has no stable ground state. Above the α axis there are two distinct regions separated by a *critical curve*. To the right of the critical curve we have the symmetric phase, and to its left we have the broken-symmetric phase. The critical curve starts at the *Gaussian critical point*, which is the origin of the (α, λ) plane, and proceeds more or less linearly to infinity with $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ and $\alpha \rightarrow -\infty$. At the arc at infinity in this direction the theory reduces to the Ising model in d dimensions, with its parameter associated to θ , in the interval $(0, \pi/2)$. In this limit the action shown in Equation (4) can be reduced to that of the Ising model, given by $-\beta \sum_{\ell} \psi_{\oplus} \psi_{\ominus}$, where $\psi = \pm 1$ and $\beta = \cot(\theta)$.

The critical curve divides the upper half of the diagram in two regions, which constitute the two phases of the theory, when interpreted as a statistical model. The transition from one phase to the other is a second-order phase transitions, in which the order parameter varies continuously across the critical curve in the $N \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ continuum limit. At the critical curve we have that $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda) \rightarrow 0$ when we take the $N \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ continuum limit. The symmetric phase is characterized by having $v_R \rightarrow 0$ in the continuum limit, while in the broken-symmetric phase we have $v_R \neq 0$ when we take the continuum limit, but the behavior of v_R in this limit is quite discontinuous, since due to the drift on finite lattices it is zero all over the parameter plane, for any finite value of N .

The continuum limits can be represented by paths in this diagram, which we call *flows*. All limits of physical interest, which must result in a finite renormalized mass m_R , converge to some point on the critical curve, where $\alpha_R \rightarrow 0$ in the continuum limit. The ensemble of the theory is Gaussian in the positive half-axis $\alpha \geq 0$, $\lambda = 0$, where we have the free theory, and the continuum limits of this free theory flow to the left along this half-axis, converging to the Gaussian critical point $\alpha = 0$, $\lambda = 0$, where the critical curve begins. In the neighborhood of the Gaussian critical point the critical curve differs very little from a straight line. This is also true asymptotically, for very large r .

2.4 Triviality on the Lattice

According to all available data, this theory has the important property of being trivial. This does not mean that it is easy or simple to deal with it, but rather alludes to the fact that, although for $\lambda > 0$ the theory is not Gaussian, the complete set of its correlation functions, and in fact all its relevant observables, can be obtained by means of a related Gaussian model, with a purely quadratic action, but with a different value of the parameter α , which must be positive, and with $\lambda = 0$, of course, as well as some arbitrarily given value of the expectation value $v_R = \langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle$ of the field. Triviality means that the theory generates only these two non-trivial and non-zero fundamental expectation values in the continuum limit, the expectation value v_R of the dimensionless field leading to the expectation value $\langle \phi(\vec{x}) \rangle$ of the dimensionfull field, and the dimensionless renormalized mass parameter α_R leading to the dimensionfull renormalized mass m_R , while we always have that $\lambda_R = 0$, leading to $\Lambda_R = 0$, at least for the cases $d \geq 4$, for the *renormalized coupling constant*, in any continuum limit.

The issue of triviality is usually discussed in the continuum limit, in terms of the dimensionfull renormalized coupling constant Λ_R . Since we have that $\Lambda_R = a^{d-4}\lambda_R$, in terms of λ_R this discussion changes depending on the dimension of spacetime. For $d > 4$ we have that $\Lambda_R \rightarrow 0$ in the continuum limit even if λ_R is simply finite in that limit (as it certainly must be), due to the extra factors of a multiplying λ_R , given that $a \rightarrow 0$ in the limit. This makes the discussion somewhat simpler in this case, resulting in trivial theories in the continuum limit, as was proved in [2,3]. In the case $d = 4$ the discussion is the same in terms of either Λ_R or λ_R , since in this case they are equal to one another. This fact makes the $d = 4$ case particularly difficult, and due to this there is still no complete proof of triviality in this case. In the case $d = 3$, since we have that $\Lambda_R = \lambda_R/a$, we may have $\Lambda_R \neq 0$ in the continuum limit even if $\lambda_R \rightarrow 0$, so long as λ_R does not go to zero too fast along the limit.

The numerical probes into the issue of triviality are usually done in terms of the momentum-space four-point function, and of its factorization properties in terms of the two-point function. These are, however, typically much more difficult from the numerical point of view, involving larger statistical errors and other numerical difficulties. Any di-

rect measurement of the renormalized coupling constant λ_R is intrinsically more difficult because it constitutes the process of measuring a zero by a statistical process involving random fluctuations and errors. In this paper we will approach the problem from the point of view of the two-point function alone, and of the measurements of the renormalized mass parameter α_R by means both of the two-point function in momentum space and of the local observables to be described in the subsequent Section 3.

The numerical experience, as we will show in this paper, indicates that the central observable of the $\lambda\phi^4$ theory in momentum space, known as the two-point function or the propagator, has a form similar to that of the same quantity in the free theory, and that it can be expressed with very good precision as

$$\left\langle |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})|^2 \right\rangle_N = \frac{R(\alpha, \lambda)}{N^d [\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)]}, \quad (27)$$

where the *residue* $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ and the renormalized square mass parameter $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$ are functions of the free parameters of the theory as indicated, and where the eigenvalues of the discrete Laplacian are given by $-\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$, where

$$\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) = \sum_{\mu=1}^d \rho_\mu^2(\vec{\kappa}), \quad (28)$$

$$\rho_\mu(\vec{\kappa}) = 2 \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{N} \kappa_\mu\right). \quad (29)$$

Note that in Equation (27) we omitted the subtractions of the propagator, because in our circumstances here we have that $\langle \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa}) \rangle = 0$. The eigenvalues of the discrete Laplacian are related to the dimensionfull linear momentum variable p_μ by

$$\rho_\mu(\vec{\kappa}) = p_\mu(\vec{\kappa})a. \quad (30)$$

In the $N \rightarrow \infty$, $a \rightarrow 0$ continuum limit at constant L this reduces to the usual form of the linear momentum within a box of size L , namely $p_\mu(\vec{\kappa}) = 2\pi\kappa_\mu/L$. By measuring numerically the propagator on the left-hand side of Equation (27), for all $\vec{\kappa}$, we are able to obtain the values of R and α_R , if we simply fit the numerical results to the formula in the right-hand side of Equation (27). The accuracy of the fit will give us information about the quality of the representation of the propagator by the expression shown in the right-hand side of Equation (27). In principle this fit includes the zero mode, but we will explicitly avoid including the zero mode in the fit. We do this because the zero mode is sensitive to the process of symmetry breaking that leads to the phase transition, and is changed by the phase transition when one passes from the symmetric phase to the broken-symmetric phase. Since the Fourier modes are all orthogonal to one another, all other modes are insensitive to the phase transition and to the behavior of the zero mode. The remaining modes are more than enough to determine R and α_R very well, even on very small lattices.

Note that, since it involves all the modes on the lattice, this kind of measurement of α_R is global to the whole lattice, and not local to any particular geometrical element of it. Note also that if it results from this fit that $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ is a positive real constant independent of $\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$, for all α and all λ , even if it is not always the value of 1, which is the exact result of the free theory with its Gaussian ensemble, then this would already constitute strong evidence towards the triviality of the theory. This is so because the existence of a constant value of R different from 1 means only that the field of the related Gaussian model has to be rescaled by \sqrt{R} , and does not spoil the fact that the action of that related model is quadratic, and therefore that the related model is Gaussian. One can obtain the exact

action of the free theory in terms of a rescaled field $\varphi' = \varphi/\sqrt{R}$. This simply means that the non-linear theory under scrutiny here undergoes a *field renormalization*. In the following Section 3 we will present some local observables that will also allow us to measure α_R . As we will see, in the case of some of these local observables there is significant evidence that triviality is in fact realized exactly on finite lattices, rather than just in the continuum limit.

3 Local Observables

Here we will develop a set of local observables that depend on the value of the dimensionless renormalized mass parameter α_R . We start in the free theory, where these observables can be calculated exactly on each finite lattice, by analytic means. In the free theory, in which we make $\lambda = 0$ and use the renormalized value α_R of the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory for the parameter α , and for which we have the complete exact solution of the theory and can therefore calculate any required quantities, it is not difficult to show that the exact solution for the two-point function in momentum space is given by

$$\left\langle |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{k})|^2 \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d [\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R]}. \quad (31)$$

It is also not difficult to show that from this result it follows that the exact solution for the two-point function in position space is given by

$$\left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}')\varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}}^{N^d} \frac{\cos\left[\frac{2\pi}{N}\vec{k} \cdot (\vec{n}' - \vec{n})\right]}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (32)$$

Next, from this result we may obtain the correlations between the values of the field at two different lattice sites located close together, both across single links and across single diagonals of plaquettes, as well as the width of the local distribution of values of the field at single sites. If we make $\vec{n}' = \vec{n}$ we get at once from Equation (32)

$$\left\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}}^{N^d} \frac{1}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (33)$$

Since on finite lattices we have that $\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle = 0$, this is the width of the local distribution of values of the field at a single site \vec{n} . It is noteworthy that this quantity has a finite and non-zero value in the continuum limit, a value that does not depend on the value that m_R has in that limit, so long as that value is finite and non-zero. This is caused by the fact that $\alpha_R \rightarrow 0$ in any continuum limit that results in a finite value for the renormalized mass m_R . Note that this observable does not really depend on the position \vec{n} . In the case of the links between two next neighbors, if we make $\vec{n}' = \vec{n} + 1_\mu$, we have from Equation (32), for the correlation over links,

$$\left\langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu)\varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}}^{N^d} \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{N}\kappa_\mu\right)}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (34)$$

Note that again this observable does not depend on the position \vec{n} . In the case of the diagonals of plaquettes, if we make $\vec{n}' = \vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu$ we have from Equation (32), for the correlation over plaquette diagonals,

$$\left\langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu)\varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}}^{N^d} \frac{\cos\left[\frac{2\pi}{N}(\kappa_\mu \pm \kappa_\nu)\right]}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (35)$$

Note that once more this observable does not depend on the position \vec{n} . It is also very simple to generalize these expressions to diagonals of higher-dimensional elementary lattice objects, such as three-dimensional cells, in the spacetime dimensions d in which they exist.

Other important and useful observables can be constructed using the finite differences of the fields at the two ends of links or plaquette diagonals. While these finite differences can have either positive or negative values, and due to the symmetries of the theory the corresponding expectation values average out to zero, their squares have non-zero averages, can easily be measured, and hence can also be used to determine the renormalized mass parameter α_R . By expanding the squares of the differences these observables can be written in terms of those shown in Equations (33), (34) and (35), and in this way we obtain for the squared differences over links

$$\left\langle [\varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) - \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{\kappa}}^{N^d} \frac{4 \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{N} \kappa_\mu\right)}{\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (36)$$

and for the squared differences over plaquette diagonals

$$\left\langle [\varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) - \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 \right\rangle_N = \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{\kappa}}^{N^d} \frac{4 \sin^2\left[\frac{\pi}{N}(\kappa_\mu \pm \kappa_\nu)\right]}{\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (37)$$

The results shown in Equations (33) through (37) are all exact results of the free theory, and their validity does depend on the theory being in fact the free theory, with its Gaussian ensemble. All the expressions shown in the right-hand sides of these equations are functions of α_R , so that by measuring numerically the functions on the left-hand sides, in the non-linear theory, and then solving the equations for α_R defined by the functions on the right-hand sides, we have several different ways of measuring the renormalized mass parameter α_R . The resulting equations for α_R can be solved numerically without too much difficulty. Of course, one can only expect these measurements to be successful if the non-linear theory is in fact trivial.

In order to account for the possible necessity of field renormalization, that is, for the possibility that we have for the residue of the propagator $R(\alpha, \lambda) \neq 1$, a different but related set of observables can be used. Taking the results for the residue R obtained from the momentum-space measurements, we may use instead of Equations (33) through (37), the following five relations between the measured functions in the non-linear theory and the results of the free theory. For the squared fields at sites we have

$$\left\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N = R \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{\kappa}}^{N^d} \frac{1}{\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (38)$$

for the correlation over links we have

$$\left\langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N = R \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{\kappa}}^{N^d} \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{N} \kappa_\mu\right)}{\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (39)$$

for the correlation over plaquette diagonals we have

$$\left\langle \varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N = R \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{\kappa}}^{N^d} \frac{\cos\left[\frac{2\pi}{N}(\kappa_\mu \pm \kappa_\nu)\right]}{\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (40)$$

for the squared differences over links we have

$$\left\langle [\varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) - \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 \right\rangle_N = R \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}} \frac{4 \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{N} \kappa_\mu\right)}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (41)$$

and for the squared differences over plaquette diagonals we have

$$\left\langle [\varphi(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) - \varphi(\vec{n})]^2 \right\rangle_N = R \frac{1}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}} \frac{4 \sin^2\left[\frac{\pi}{N}(\kappa_\mu \pm \kappa_\nu)\right]}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (42)$$

If we write the expectation values of the non-linear theory in the left-hand sides in terms of a renormalized field $\varphi' = \varphi/\sqrt{R}$, then the multiplicative renormalization factors \sqrt{R} of the fields cancel off, and we end up with the results of the free theory related to the renormalized field of the non-linear theory. In writing these expressions we must recall that the squared-field observables $\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \rangle_N$, $\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n} + 1_\mu) \rangle_N$ and $\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n} + 1_\mu \pm 1_\nu) \rangle_N$ at single sites are all equal, since these expectation values do not really depend on the position \vec{n} .

While the result obtained from the momentum-space expression in Equation (27) is necessarily a global one, valid for the lattice as a whole, those obtained from the position-space expressions in Equations from (33) through (42) are all local, being valid for particular sites, links or plaquette diagonals, as the case may be. If we introduce into the theory a position-dependent external source $j(\vec{n})$, then all these local quantities will in fact depend on the position \vec{n} , as well as on the direction μ , and then the global results for α_R obtained from Equation (27) lose much of their significance. However, even in this case the local observables can still be used, so long as we write them in terms of the *subtracted* correlation functions when necessary, such as in

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\langle \left[\varphi(\vec{n}') - \langle \varphi(\vec{n}') \rangle_N \right] \left[\varphi(\vec{n}) - \langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle_N \right] \right\rangle_N \\ &= \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}') \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N - \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}') \right\rangle_N \left\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \right\rangle_N. \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

Of course in such a case there is no trouble in doing this, since in the presence of any external source $j(\vec{n})$ the random lattice drift stops, and then the expectation values of the fields seen above become well-defined and easily measurable. This shows that the local observables for the parameter α_R are potentially very useful ones. We will use the symbol α_R for the value obtained from the propagator in momentum space, $\alpha_{R,s}$ for the value obtained from the width at sites, $\alpha_{R,\ell}$ for the value obtained from correlations over links, $\alpha_{R,d}$ for the value obtained from correlations over plaquette diagonals, $\alpha_{R,\Delta\ell}$ for the value obtained from squared differences over links, and $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$ for the value obtained from squared differences over plaquette diagonals.

In this paper we will emphasize primarily the measurements of α_R obtained from Equations (41) and (42), since these observables are insensitive to the behavior of the zero mode and thus to the phenomenon of spontaneous symmetry breaking that exists in the quartic scalar theories. So long as we have a constant expectation value of the field, which is expressed as a non-zero coefficient of the zero mode, these observables are insensitive to the behavior of this zero mode, since if we add a non-zero vacuum expectation value to the field, this constant term would cancel off in the difference of the two fields at the two ends of the link or plaquette diagonal. Due to this these two observables will return the correct values of α_R both in the symmetric phase and in the broken-symmetric phase. The other three observables give essentially the same correct results in the symmetric phase, but are significantly distorted by the spontaneous symmetry breaking mechanism in the broken-symmetric phase.

Since in this paper we will not introduce any external sources at all, the results shown in Equations from (33) through (42) will all be independent of position. In this case we can compare them to the global result in Equations (27), as a further test of the triviality of the theory. In such a situation we may also, in each case, average the values obtained for the squared fields, the correlation functions and the squared difference functions, over all sites, all links or all diagonals, as the case may be, with the objective of further improving the statistical quality of these results.

4 Description of the Program

Here we will give a general description of the numerical programs used to generate the data shown in the graphs presented in the subsequent Section 5. There are several programs involved, and the whole set is freely available on the Web, where it is being distributed under the GNU GPL. A compressed `tar` file with all the programs, auxiliary files and documentation can be easily and freely downloaded from Zenodo [4]. The programs have been developed and tested only of the Linux operating system, but it should not be too difficult to port then to other Unix-like operating systems. Overall there are about 7000 lines of Fortran code in a little more than 150 modules, and a few C modules for interface with the Linux system calls. The contents of the `tar` file should work right out of the box in any Linux system that has the necessary development software installed, such as the GNU Fortran compiler `gfortran`, the GNU C compiler `gcc` and the `make` utility. The programs run with standard double-precision (64-bit) real variables. The source code is extensively documented internally by comment lines, and there is a `README` file with the basic instructions for compiling and running the programs.

The stochastic simulations are worked out in two phases, in the first of which a randomly chosen initial configuration of the field is relaxed to a typical one for the set of free parameters in use, and in the second of which statistical samplings are collected. There are two main Monte Carlo programs, one called `Main_relaxer` for the relaxation phase and one called `Main_sampler` for the sampling phase. In the relaxation phase we also run a couple of feedback mechanisms in order to adjust two technical parameters, the range of the random walk in the Metropolis algorithm and the number of clusters in the Wolff cluster algorithm, in order to ensure that the acceptance rates of both the Metropolis updates and the Wolff cluster updates are kept as close as possible to 50%, in order to maximize the efficiency of the process of diffusion of the Markovian chain through the space of configurations. This works well almost always, the exception being deep in the broken-symmetric phase, where the Wolff clusters span essentially the whole lattice, so that the Wolff cluster acceptance rate approaches 100% even with the construction of only a single cluster.

There are a few additional processing phases after the statistical sampling phase is finished. The additional programs are meant to do basic statistical analysis of the results, such as the calculation of the final averages and of their standard statistical errors, which is what the program `Main_aversig` does, and then to do the data analysis, with a program called `Main_propres` for the results relating to the momentum-space propagator, including the fits in momentum space, and another program called `Main_lobres` for the results relating to the local observables. In these last two phases equivalent data is consolidated, in order to improve the statistical quality of the results. In the program `Main_propres` data for different values of \vec{k} that result in the same value of the eigenvalue $-\rho^2(\vec{k})$ of the Laplacian operator are consolidated. In the program `Main_lobres` geometrically equivalent data are consolidated over sites, links and plaquette diagonals, as allowed by the intrinsic symmetries of the problem.

This type of consolidation is possible, and further decreases the statistical errors in the data, because these measurements are related by symmetry transformations under which the theory is invariant, and because they are, by and large, statistically independent from one another. In the case of the measurements in momentum space the various measurements which are consolidated are equivalent because the propagator can depend on the modes $\vec{\kappa}$ only through the eigenvalues $-\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$ of the Laplacian, and not directly on the values of the individual integer coordinates κ_μ . In this case the statistical independence of the various measurements is related to the very fact that the theory is trivial, and hence does not couple different lattice modes, as we can verify a posteriori.

In the case of the measurements associated with the local observables, the various measurements which are consolidated are equivalent because they are related to each other by the discrete translation and rotation invariances of the lattice. In this case they are almost completely statistically independent because there is very little correlation between the fields at different sites. In fact, it is possible to show that in the continuum limit the fields at two different sites become completely uncorrelated from one another. A simple proof of this fact, based on the physical requirements on the two-point Green's function that are necessary for any well-behaved quantum field theory in the continuum limit, can be found in Appendix A.

The program that runs the longest is `Main_sampler`, specially if the lattice is large and high-precision statistics are required. The numerical work presented in this paper involved approximately 400,000 hours of CPU time on a single 4 GHz processor. This program is prepared to run in parallel on many CPUs or cores of a multiprocessing machine, as well as on many nodes of a parallel machine, such as a cluster of processing nodes. Due to the parallelization the actual wall-clock time for producing the data was reduced to approximately 1500 hours, or about 2 months. Each instance of the program on a given processor writes out sampling data for each one of the observables, with one sample per line in the output data files. All this is done within a well-structured standardized sub-directory tree. There are control files that record the number of processors involved in a particular run and the number of sub-averages already produced for that run, as well as various log files. Once a particular run is done, all the output files, for each one of the various observables, one from each processor, can be concatenated together in a single consolidated output data file, including the contributions from all processors, for that observable. Included in the source code `tar` file there is a shell script called `collect_parallel_data` that does this.

The Monte Carlo program uses two different algorithms in order to update the field configurations and create a Markovian chain of configurations. The direction of the field values, which in our case here is just their orientations, as given by their signs, is updated by the *Wolff cluster algorithm* [5], which is the most effective one for this purpose, since it is numerically efficient and essentially eliminates any troublesome auto-correlations along the Markovian chain. In order to update the magnitude of the fields we use the *Metropolis algorithm* [6], with the lattice set in what is called a *checkerboarding* configuration, in which we separate the sites into two groups of mutually independent sites, the odd sites and the even sites, as defined by the parity of the sum of all their d integer coordinates n_μ . In this way we have that every next-neighbor of an even site is an odd site, and vice-versa. This allows us to update one group all at once, while keeping the other group fixed, and hence to avoid giving origin to unwanted correlations within that group, along the Markovian chain. Due to this, and given that we use periodic boundary conditions on the lattice, we are able to use only even values of N , starting at $N = 2$, because otherwise the separation of the sites into two mutually non-interacting groups would be impossible.

Monte Carlo programs can be parallelized in a trivial way, since it is enough to have each

independent processor generate independent sub-averages towards a global total average. Each processor can do this in a completely independent fashion, without depending on other processors at all, and will produce statistically independent results so long as the process at each processor uses a different value of the random seed. The seed for the random number generator will be chosen and periodically changed, from each sub-average to the next, using the true random number generator `/dev/urandom` of the Linux operating system, that does this by collecting entropy during the operation of the hardware, and thus keeping and using a cache of entropy. The use of this native Linux random number generator is probably the greatest difficulty in porting the programs to other operating systems, in which this system facility may not be available.

The implementation in the program of the Fourier transform and its inverse presents particular challenges. This transform is represented by a very large double-precision real matrix, of dimensions $N^d \times N^d$, with elements involving either exponential functions or sines and cosines. Since the Fourier transformation is executed many times, the repeated calculation of these matrix elements becomes very expensive in terms of processing time. On the other hand, only a relatively small collection of different real numbers appears in these matrix elements, each one being repeated many times along them. The solution adopted was to calculate these real numbers only once, then store the small number of different values of these elements, and use them in the transformation matrix via an indexation system, which maps the integer coordinates of each matrix element to the corresponding double-precision real value. In this way a very large number of dynamical real numbers was traded for a much smaller number of static real numbers, plus the corresponding integers that are the addresses of those real numbers in the transformation matrix. These indexation integers are also static, and can be defined as short (16-bit) integers, further reducing the memory size requirements.

The idea of integer indexation is also used for several other ends in the program, such as making contiguous lists of even and odd sites, contiguous lists of the neighbors of even and odd sites, contiguous lists of the neighbors of arbitrary sites, and contiguous lists of sites, links and plaquette diagonals. The use of such indexation matrices makes the program both more efficient and easier to read, so long as the names of the variables involved are judiciously chosen.

In this program the definition of a single sweep of the lattice, for the acquisition of a single sample, consists of three parts, first a single trial at the Metropolis update of every single even site, then a single trial at the Metropolis update of every single odd site, and finally the construction of a certain number of Wolff clusters, to ensure that every site was tested once, on average, to be flipped as part of a cluster. The samplings were organized in sub-averages of a global average, to enable us to calculate the dispersion of the sub-averages around the total average, and therefore to evaluate the standard statistical errors of the final averages. We used large sub-averages, of 25000 sweeps each, with a total of 1000 such sub-averages. This corresponds to 25×10^6 sweeps in total, and to that same number of samples, thus corresponding to a nominal statistical error level of 1 in 5000, or 0.02%.

It should be noted here that the `Main_sampler` program makes rather extensive use of disk space. Even moderately large lattices can easily produce more than 1 TB of raw data on large statistics runs. When concatenating the various output data files from individual processors into a single global output data file, this disk space requirement will momentarily double. After the calculation of the global averages and of their standard statistical errors by the program `Main_aversig`, in the statistical analysis phase, the raw data can then be deleted, which will radically reduce the disk space requirements for permanent storage of the final results and their standard errors.

5 Numerical Results

The numerical results presented here can be classified as being of two basic types. First we have the results in momentum space, as presented in the development of the theory that was given in Section 2. Then we have the results in position space, based on the local observables defined and discussed in Section 3. The results in momentum space are all based on the fits to the propagator, from which we obtain the residue $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ of the pole of the propagator and the renormalized mass parameter $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$, according on the expression presented in Equation (27). The results obtained in momentum space for the residue $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ are subsequently used in the expressions for the local observables in position space. Therefore our first task here is to document the quality of these momentum-space fits. After that, we can report on the behavior of the results in momentum space, and finally on the behavior of the results in position space.

Due to the inevitable space limitations, only a rather limited set of graphs with the numerical results will be shown here. A much more complete set of processed data and formatted graphs is available on the network, and can be obtained by free download from Zenodo [7]. The statistically processed data are available in readable text format, and the formatted data in graph format are available in a couple of readable vector formats, than can be easily plotted and even manipulated. With the use of the free graphics application `xmgrace` one can perform many useful operations on the data, such as zooming in, thus blowing the graphs up in order to look at small details.

5.1 Fits to the Propagator

Given the momentum-space propagator as calculated by the stochastic programs, we need to obtain from it the two essential observables, the residue $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ of the pole and the renormalized mass parameter $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$. In the general case the propagator $\tilde{g}_2(\vec{\kappa})$ is defined as the subtracted two-point function in momentum space,

$$\tilde{g}_2(\vec{\kappa}) = \left\langle |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})|^2 \right\rangle - |\langle \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa}) \rangle|^2, \quad (44)$$

however, since in our case here, given that we are working on finite lattices without external sources or fixed boundary conditions, we always have for the expectation value of the field at sites $\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle = 0$ for all \vec{n} , which implies at once that $\langle \tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa}) \rangle = 0$ for all $\vec{\kappa}$, we can in fact simply use

$$\tilde{g}_2(\vec{\kappa}) = \left\langle |\tilde{\varphi}(\vec{\kappa})|^2 \right\rangle. \quad (45)$$

In all cases of interest here this function can be well fitted by the expression of the propagator of the free theory, for all strictly positive values of $\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$, with modified values of $R(\alpha, \lambda)$, which is just 1 in the free theory, and $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$, which is just the parameter α in the free theory. Since our objective here is to obtain the values of $R(\alpha, \lambda)$ and $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)$ from the numerical data, we consider this function normalized in the form $N^d \tilde{g}_2(\vec{\kappa})$, and then invert it, thus obtaining the function $f(\vec{\kappa})$ in momentum space, representing the inverted and appropriately rescaled propagator,

$$\begin{aligned} f(\vec{\kappa}) &= \frac{1}{N^d \tilde{g}_2(\vec{\kappa})} \\ &= \frac{\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda)}{R(\alpha, \lambda)} + \frac{1}{R(\alpha, \lambda)} \rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) \\ &= a_0(\alpha, \lambda) + a_1(\alpha, \lambda) \rho^2(\vec{\kappa}), \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

where $a_0(\alpha, \lambda)$ and $a_1(\alpha, \lambda)$ are now the two parameters of a linear fit in terms of $\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$, and where $f(\vec{\kappa})$ may also be written as $f(\rho^2)$. Once $a_0(\alpha, \lambda)$ and $a_1(\alpha, \lambda)$ are determined, the residue of the pole is given by $R(\alpha, \lambda) = 1/a_1(\alpha, \lambda)$ and the mass parameter is given by $\alpha_R(\alpha, \lambda) = a_0(\alpha, \lambda)/a_1(\alpha, \lambda)$. In addition to this, since the functions above depend only on the eigenvalues of the Laplacian $\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$, and there are several different modes $\vec{\kappa}$ that result in the same value of $\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$, we can consolidate the values of the function $f(\vec{\kappa}) = f(\rho^2)$ in terms of the values of $\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$, taking averages and propagating the errors appropriately. This results in a certain number n of independent values of $\rho^2(\vec{\kappa})$, which we will denote by x_i , for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Note that we start the counter i at one, which means that we exclude the zero-mode $\vec{\kappa} = \vec{0}$, with $\rho^2(\vec{\kappa}) = 0$. We therefore have the function in this notation, leaving aside the dependencies on α and λ for the time being,

$$f(x_i) = a_0 + a_1 x_i. \quad (47)$$

The problem of finding R , α_R and their standard errors is thus reduced to the problem of finding a_0 , a_1 and their standard errors. This can be done by the procedure of fitting the numerical data to the linear expression given in Equation (47) above. We therefore have a χ^2 -fit minimization problem, with the n data points $y_i = 1/[N^d \tilde{g}_{2,i}]$ to be compared to the fitting function $f_i = f(x_i)$ at the positions $x_i = \rho_i^2$. Given that the standard errors σ_i associated to the data points y_i can vary significantly with the values of i , we will use the weighted version of the χ^2 function, which is defined as

$$\chi^2(a_0, a_1) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{a_0 + a_1 x_i - y_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2. \quad (48)$$

It is important to emphasize here that we will use only the range $i = 1, \dots, n$ for the data points, avoiding the value $i = 0$, which is the zero mode, because it gets severely entangled with the symmetry breaking process. The use of these weights can be interpreted in several ways. First, this is a way to give more influence over the overall result of the fitting process to those terms that have smaller errors and therefore are more precise. Second, this makes the sum defining $\chi^2(a_0, a_1)$ intrinsically dimensionless, regardless of the physical units or nature of the quantities involved. Third, when we consolidate physically equivalent terms and propagate errors, this automatically uses the fact that a particular value of i refers to the average of several independent measurements, and increases its influence accordingly, since under Gaussian error propagation σ_i^2 decreases linearly with the number of consolidated observations, so that $1/\sigma_i^2$ effectively counts the number of measurements that were consolidated in a particular value of i .

The function $\chi^2(a_0, a_1)$ is a positive function that goes to infinity in every limit to infinity along the (a_0, a_1) plane, in any direction. It is a continuous and differentiable function of both a_0 and a_1 , and therefore has a single point of minimum. The position of this minimum can be obtained analytically, if we consider the two partial derivatives of $\chi^2(a_0, a_1)$ with respect to a_0 and a_1 ,

$$\frac{\partial \chi^2}{\partial a_0} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{a_0 + a_1 x_i - y_i}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (49)$$

$$\frac{\partial \chi^2}{\partial a_1} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{a_0 + a_1 x_i - y_i}{\sigma_i^2} x_i. \quad (50)$$

The condition determining the location of the extremal point is that both partial derivatives be zero at the point of minimum, which can be used to determine a_0 and a_1 , resulting in the pair of linear equations

$$a_0 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \right) + a_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right), \quad (51)$$

$$a_0 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) + a_1 \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2} \right) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right), \quad (52)$$

which forms quite a simple linear system of equations. This can easily be solved for a_0 and a_1 . Multiplying Equations (51) and (52) by appropriate factors and subtracting these two equations in order to eliminate a_1 we get for a_0 ,

$$a_0 = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right)}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2} \right) - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right)^2}. \quad (53)$$

All these sums can be calculated numerically in a straightforward manner. Multiplying now the same Equations (51) and (52) by other appropriate factors and subtracting these two equations in order to eliminate a_0 we get for a_1 ,

$$a_1 = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right)}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2} \right) - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2} \right)^2}. \quad (54)$$

Again all these sums can be calculated in a straightforward manner. Note that the denominator is the same as in Equation (53), and that it does not depend on the data points y_i . Note also that all the sums are quite simple and follow a regular pattern. There is one sum without x_i or y_i , there are two sums with powers of x_i only, one sum with only y_i and one sum with the product $x_i y_i$, which we denote as

$$\Sigma_{x^0 y^0} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (55)$$

$$\Sigma_{x^1 y^0} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (56)$$

$$\Sigma_{x^2 y^0} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i^2}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (57)$$

$$\Sigma_{x^0 y^1} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (58)$$

$$\Sigma_{x^1 y^1} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i y_i}{\sigma_i^2}. \quad (59)$$

In terms of these quantities our results can be written as

$$a_0 = \frac{\Sigma_{x^2 y^0} \Sigma_{x^0 y^1} - \Sigma_{x^1 y^0} \Sigma_{x^1 y^1}}{\Sigma_{x^0 y^0} \Sigma_{x^2 y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1 y^0}^2}, \quad (60)$$

$$a_1 = \frac{\Sigma_{x^0 y^0} \Sigma_{x^1 y^1} - \Sigma_{x^1 y^0} \Sigma_{x^0 y^1}}{\Sigma_{x^0 y^0} \Sigma_{x^2 y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1 y^0}^2}. \quad (61)$$

There are two types of errors involved in the fitting process. On the one hand there is the overall fitting error, which describes how well the analytical expression used fits the data. On the other hand there is the uncertainty in the values of a_0 and a_1 due to the numerical errors σ_i of y_i . These last ones can be calculated by straightforward propagation of errors. In order to do this we need to calculate the partial derivatives of a_0 and a_1 with respect to y_j . Since y_i does not appear in the denominator of our results in Equations (53) and (54), this calculation is quite simple, and we get

$$\frac{\partial a_0}{\partial y_j} = \frac{1}{\sigma_j^2} \frac{\Sigma_{x^2 y^0} - x_j \Sigma_{x^1 y^0}}{\Sigma_{x^0 y^0} \Sigma_{x^2 y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1 y^0}^2}, \quad (62)$$

$$\frac{\partial a_1}{\partial y_j} = \frac{1}{\sigma_j^2} \frac{x_j \Sigma_{x^0 y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1 y^0}}{\Sigma_{x^0 y^0} \Sigma_{x^2 y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1 y^0}^2}. \quad (63)$$

Using the standard formula for the propagation of errors we now get, after some rather remarkable cancellations and simplifications

$$\sigma_{a_0} = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma_{x^2 y^0}}{\Sigma_{x^0 y^0} \Sigma_{x^2 y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1 y^0}^2}}, \quad (64)$$

$$\sigma_{a_1} = \sqrt{\frac{\Sigma_{x^0 y^0}}{\Sigma_{x^0 y^0} \Sigma_{x^2 y^0} - \Sigma_{x^1 y^0}^2}}. \quad (65)$$

Therefore, after some lengthy algebraic work we get simple formulas for both the coefficients and their errors, always with the same denominator.

The other type of error, relating to the fit as a whole, can be estimated by comparing areas. If we interpolate the discrete functions f_i and y_i by continuous functions over a range of values of ρ^2 , we can then consider comparing the two areas under the curves of the graphs of these functions, one for the fitting function and another for the data. The area between these two curves, compared to the area under one of them, will tell us how good the fit is. In our discrete environment here what we can do is to look at the differences between the fitting function f_i and the data y_i , over the range $i = 1, \dots, n$,

$$\Delta_i = f_i - y_i, \quad (66)$$

where the fitting function f_i is given in Equation (47). Since we do not want variations with opposite signs to cancel each other, we consider the sum of the squares of these differences, which has the dimensions of squared area,

$$(\Delta S)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (f_i - y_i)^2. \quad (67)$$

Note that this is essentially the definition of the χ^2 function, so that we will actually use the usual weighted definition of this function, for the same reasons as before,

$$(\Delta S)^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_i - y_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2, \quad (68)$$

which in principle should be divided by the normalization factor

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}. \quad (69)$$

Global Fitting Errors			
$\Delta S/S$	$d = 3$	$d = 4$	$d = 5$
$N = 2$	3.1389×10^{-4}	3.0615×10^{-4}	2.2366×10^{-4}
$N = 4$	2.1905×10^{-4}	0.9212×10^{-4}	0.4239×10^{-4}
$N = 6$	2.0070×10^{-4}	0.6554×10^{-4}	—————
$N = 8$	2.0195×10^{-4}	0.6779×10^{-4}	—————

Table 1: Average of the global fitting errors, taken over a significant part of the parameter plane. The errors are given by $\Delta S/S$, and these results show that they are compatible with the statistical errors of the simulations.

However, since we are going to compare this quantity to another average of the same type, with the same normalization factor, we may ignore this normalization factor for now. As a reference value for this quantity we compare it to the weighted squared area S^2 under the fitting function, defined in the same way,

$$S^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2, \quad (70)$$

which should also be divided by the normalization factor given in Equation (69). We thus get the ratio representing the quality of the fit,

$$\frac{\Delta S}{S} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\Delta_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{f_i}{\sigma_i} \right)^2}}. \quad (71)$$

This number, on a scale given by the interval $[0, 1]$, will give us an idea of how good the fit is, that is, of how well the data is represented by the function used for the fit. The value zero indicates a perfect fit. It is to be expected that this quantity cannot be significantly smaller than the relative statistical errors which are intrinsic to the number of samplings used in the statistics, in our case here 2×10^{-4} , possibly divided by the square root of the number of consolidated entries in each case. In Table 1 one can see the average value of $\Delta S/S$, calculated over a significant part of the (C, π_e) parameter plane, for each dimension d and for each lattice size N . The global fitting errors are smaller for the larger lattices because in these cases we have a larger number of equivalent data that were consolidated together. As one can see, these overall fitting errors are essentially compatible with the expected statistical fluctuations of the runs, so that the fits are essentially perfect within the statistical expectations.

In Figure 2 we can see three examples of the fit to the inverted propagator in a few typical cases, with $d = 4$, $N = 8$, $r = 1.0$ and three values of θ , with $\theta = 30^\circ$ in the broken-symmetric phase, $\theta = 60^\circ$ near the phase transition, and $\theta = 120^\circ$ in the symmetric phase. In this graph the data points are represented by the symbols and the linear fits are represented by the lines. The behavior of the fitting function and of the data, as well as the quality of the fit, are essentially the same in all other cases. This graph is meant only at giving an illustrative visual idea of the quality of the fits. The fits shown were calculated numerically by the graphics package, instead of by the exact analytical approach described

Fits of the Inverted Propagator

Figure 2: Examples of the fits to the inverted propagator for $d = 4$, $N = 8$, $r = 1.0$, and the angles $\theta = 30^\circ$, $\theta = 60^\circ$ and $\theta = 120^\circ$. The data are represented by the symbols, and the fits are represented by the lines.

above, and used to construct Table 1. The correlation coefficient of the fit returned by the graphics package was always essentially equal to 1.0, indicating an excellent fit. As one can see, the data error bars are quite small, barely visible in the scale of the graph.

5.2 Results in Momentum Space

The results in momentum space were obtained by scanning the parameter space of the theory, with the use of the coordinates (r, θ) , and then using the techniques described in Subsection 5.1 in order to calculate R and α_R . In Figure 3 we can see the results for the dimensionless renormalized mass parameter α_R obtained from the momentum-space propagator, over a significant part of the parameter plane, for the case $d = 4$, $N = 8$, with $r = 0.1, \dots, 5.0$. For each curve shown the $\theta \rightarrow 0$ limit to the left side is exactly equal to twice the value of the $\theta \rightarrow \pi$ limit to the right side, which corresponds to the free theory, and is itself given by the value of r . All the curves emanate from a point close to the θ axis, which is an approximation of the position of the critical point for these values of d and N . This illustrates how we have $\alpha_R \rightsquigarrow 0$ when we increase N and approach the critical curve in the parameter plane.

In Figure 4 we can see an illustration of the first few steps towards the continuum limit, for the case $d = 4$ and $r = 1.0$, using the range $N = 2, \dots, 8$. Again we see that we have $\alpha_R \rightsquigarrow 0$ when we approach the critical point, including when we take the continuum limit. Note that the value of α_R increases to both sides from the position of the critical point. Therefore, although the position of the minimum of α_R can be used as the best evaluation

Measurements of α_R in Momentum Space

Figure 3: An example of the momentum-space propagator, for the case $d = 4$ and $N = 8$, measured over a significant part of the parameter plane.

of the position of the critical point, for given values of d and N , α_R is not really an order parameter in the usual sense. As one can see in Figure 4, the continuum limit proceeds very fast with N . This is due to the fact that the proximity to the continuum limit, in terms of the critical behavior of the lattice interpreted as a statistical system, is approximately proportional, not to N , but to the total number N^d of sites in the lattice.

The continuum limit is indeed tied up with the critical behavior of the lattice system. The behavior of the order parameter σ_0^2 defined in Equation (20) can be seen in Figure 5, for the case $d = 4$ and $r = 1.0$. In the continuum limit the order parameter tends to zero in the symmetric phase, to the right of the critical point, and remains different from zero in the broken-symmetric phase, to the left of the critical point. The curves $\sigma_0^2(\theta)$ shown diverge to infinity as $-\alpha/\lambda = \cot(\theta)$ when we make $\theta \rightarrow 0$, independently of the values of N and r . The value of these curves at the smallest value of θ that was used, which was 5° , is approximately given by $\cot(\pi/36) \simeq 11.43$, also independently of the values of N and r . As one can see, the finite-lattice curves approach a limiting curve very fast. Despite the fact that the curves diverge to infinity as we make $\theta \rightarrow 0$, they are still continuous at the critical point, including in the continuum limit. It is apparent, however, that in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit the limiting curve becomes non-differentiable at the critical point.

5.3 Results in Position Space

In Figures 6, 7 and 8 we can see some examples of the results of the various local measurements of the renormalized mass parameter α_R , for the case $d = 4$, $N = 8$ and $r = 1.0$, as well as the comparison of these with the corresponding results from momentum space. In Figure 6 we can see the results α_R from momentum space and $\alpha_{R,s}$ from the local widths of

Illustration of the Continuum Limit

Figure 4: An example of the initial part of the sequence of lattices that constitute the continuum limit, for the case $d = 4$ and $r = 1.0$.

the field at sites, as given in Equations (27) and (38). The match is quite good in the symmetric phase, but the local result detaches from the momentum-space result in the region around the critical point, and simply becomes very close to zero in the broken-symmetric case. It is important to note that this has nothing to do with zero-mass Goldstone bosons, which do not exist in this theory since its symmetry group is discrete and not continuous. This is just the interference of the symmetry breaking mechanism with the results originating from the free theory.

In Figure 7 we can see the results α_R from momentum space, as well as $\alpha_{R,\ell}$ and $\alpha_{R,\Delta\ell}$ from the local correlations and variations of the field over links, as given in Equations (27), (39) and (41). In the case of the results from the local correlation function over links the behavior is similar to that of the results from the widths at sites. The match is quite good in the symmetric phase, but detaches around the critical point and becomes close to zero in the broken-symmetric phase. In the case of the local variations over links the match is remarkably good, and extends to the whole range of values of θ , including throughout the region near the critical point. While the results for the correlation function can be seen to be very slightly below the curve of α_R from momentum space even in the symmetric phase, if we amplify the scales of the graph sufficiently, those for the variations over links match the momentum-space results with extraordinary precision. Essentially all the local-variation results coincide with the corresponding momentum-space results well within the statistical error bars of either measurement.

In Figure 8 we can see the results α_R from momentum space, as well as $\alpha_{R,d}$ and $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$ from the local correlations and variations of the field over plaquette diagonals, as given in Equations (27), (40) and (42). The situation in this case is completely analogous to

Figure 5: An example of the initial part of the approach of the order parameter σ_0^2 to the critical behavior, for the case $d = 4$ and $r = 1.0$.

that of the corresponding quantities measured over links, with the results from the local correlation functions detaching around the critical point and becoming close to zero in the broken-symmetric phase, and those from the local variations matching the momentum-space results extremely well, for all values of θ . The reason why in all these three cases, that is, of the results from the local widths at sites, from the local correlations over links and from the local correlations over diagonals, are always below the momentum-space curve, even if only very slightly so in the symmetric phase, is that the symmetry is never fully realized on finite lattices. It only becomes an exact symmetry in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit. The observables involving the local variations of the field are immune to this effect, since they are invariant under the operation of subtracting the fields.

In order to better document how well the results from the local variations over links and diagonals match the corresponding results from momentum space, we compared the absolute values of differences given by $|\alpha_R - \alpha_{R,\Delta\ell}|$ and $|\alpha_R - \alpha_{R,\Delta d}|$ with the corresponding statistical errors, propagated from the errors of the observables involved, in order to verify whether or not these differences are statistically compatible with zero. In Tables 2 and 3 we can see these results, showing that they are indeed compatible with zero. Note that all the numbers shown in these tables should be multiplied by 10^{-5} , thus indicating that both the differences and their errors are very small, and quite compatible with the general statistical error level of 2×10^{-4} of our simulations. Therefore, there are no detectable differences between the results from the local variations and from the momentum-space propagator that can be detected with the available statistics. This suggests rather strongly that these results might in fact be exact ones, on every finite N -lattice, as well as in the continuum limit.

Figure 6: Comparison of the measurements of α_R and $\alpha_{R,s}$, for the case $d = 4$, $N = 8$ and $r = 1.0$.

The deviation of the results for $\alpha_{R,s}$ associated to the local width of the fields, $\alpha_{R,\ell}$ associated to the local correlations across links and $\alpha_{R,d}$ associated to the local correlations across plaquette diagonals, from the corresponding results from momentum space, can be understood qualitatively in terms of the symmetry breaking mechanism, and the related critical behavior of the lattice system. Taking the case of the local width at sites as an example for this discussion, we recall that the value of $\alpha_{R,s}$ is to be obtained as the solution of Equation (38), when we use in its left-hand site the expectation value obtained in the non-linear theory. We may write this equation, separating the contribution of the zero mode from the rest of the sum, as

$$\langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \rangle_N = \frac{R}{N^d} \frac{1}{\alpha_R} + \frac{R}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k} \neq \vec{0}}^{N^d-1} \frac{1}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}. \quad (72)$$

If we consider the left-hand side of Equation (72) in the non-linear theory, when the symmetry breaks the value of the field at any typical site, instead of undergoing random fluctuations around zero, starts to undergo those same fluctuations around a much larger absolute value, due to the fact that the fields tend to align in some arbitrary direction. In our case here this arbitrary direction can be either positive or negative, and from the form of the potential and the position of its minima, we can see that the absolute value around which the fields now fluctuate is of the order of $\sqrt{-\alpha/\lambda}$. Therefore the value of the observable at the left-hand site of Equation (72) is of the order of $-\alpha/\lambda$, which has a positive value in the broken-symmetric phase. This value is typically quite large, and goes to infinity as $\theta \rightarrow 0$. The reason why this value is so large is that we should use in the left-hand

Figure 7: Comparison of the measurements of α_R , $\alpha_{R,\ell}$ and $\alpha_{R,\Delta\ell}$, for the case $d = 4$, $N = 8$ and $r = 1.0$, illustrating the quality of the $\alpha_{R,\Delta\ell}$ measurements.

side of Equation (72) the *subtracted* version of the observable, such as the one shown in Equation (43) with $\vec{n} = \vec{n}'$, which would be much smaller. However, due to the drift of the direction of symmetry breaking on finite lattices, we have that $\langle \varphi(\vec{n}) \rangle_N = 0$, so that the values of the quantities to be subtracted are not available to us. If we now consider the right-hand side of Equation (72), we have for the remaining sum

$$\frac{R}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k} \neq \vec{0}}^{N^d-1} \frac{1}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R} < \frac{R}{N^d} \sum_{\vec{k}}^{N^d} \frac{1}{\rho^2(\vec{k}) + \alpha_R}, \quad (73)$$

where this last sum on the right-hand side is the squared dispersion of values of the field at any arbitrarily given site \vec{n} , in the free theory, which is defined by

$$\sigma^2(N) = \langle \varphi^2(\vec{n}) \rangle_N. \quad (74)$$

On finite lattices $\sigma^2(N)$ is a finite number, or course, and in addition to this, in the cases $d \geq 3$ the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limits of these quantities exist and are finite, of the order of 1, in fact. In the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit they can be obtained with good precision by adding up progressively larger finite sums and extrapolating to $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit, while keeping the mass m_R constant, finite and non-zero, and it results that in each dimension $\sigma(\infty)$ is given approximately by

$$\begin{aligned} d = 3 : \quad \sigma(\infty) &\simeq 0.5027, \\ d = 4 : \quad \sigma(\infty) &\simeq 0.3936, \\ d = 5 : \quad \sigma(\infty) &\simeq 0.3400. \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

Figure 8: Comparison of the measurements of α_R , $\alpha_{R,d}$ and $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$, for the case $d = 4$, $N = 8$ and $r = 1.0$, illustrating the quality of the $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$ measurements.

It therefore follows that the remaining sum in Equation (72) is a limited quantity, of the order of 1. Therefore, if the left-hand side of Equation (72) is larger than this limit, the value of the remaining sum cannot match it for any value of α_R . In this case, in order to satisfy the equation, it is necessary to decrease α_R , so that the contribution of the first term on the right-hand side, which is the contribution of the zero mode, can become large enough to match the large value on the left-hand side. This is the mechanism through which the numerical resolution of Equation (38) for α_R in such cases drives the value of $\alpha_{R,s}$ towards zero. Similar arguments can be made in the cases of $\alpha_{R,\ell}$ and $\alpha_{R,d}$, as solutions of Equations (39) and (40), respectively.

In all cases it is the contribution of the zero mode, and the fact that the information for the appropriate subtractions is not available, that causes all the trouble. In order to avoid this, one way would be to run simulations in the presence of a small constant external source j . In this case all the information for the subtractions would become available, so that we would then be able to use any of the local observables developed here in order to get α_R correctly. This change would shift the values of all the observables, but would still allow us to compare them to one another, and therefore would also allow the use of all the observables given in Equations (38) through (42), for all values of θ , without the large deviations found here in the broken-symmetric phase.

6 Conclusions

The numerical results shown here, and the corresponding analysis, indicate very strongly the triviality of the $\lambda\varphi^4$ theory, not only in the already expected cases $d = 4$ and $d = 5$,

The Differences over Lattice Links and their Errors			
$(\times 10^{-5})$	$d = 3$	$d = 4$	$d = 5$
$N = 2$	3.2749 ± 276.3985	3.3593 ± 206.1028	2.6093 ± 165.5582
$N = 4$	4.4933 ± 59.9650	1.5193 ± 40.7928	0.63092 ± 27.67623
$N = 6$	4.0607 ± 28.9027	1.0104 ± 17.4449	—————
$N = 8$	4.7233 ± 18.2638	1.7913 ± 9.8056	—————

Table 2: Average differences $|\alpha_R - \alpha_{R,\Delta\ell}|$ and their errors, for the case of links, showing that the differences are compatible with zero. All numbers and errors reported are to be multiplied by 10^{-5} .

The Differences over Plaquette Diagonals and their Errors			
$(\times 10^{-5})$	$d = 3$	$d = 4$	$d = 5$
$N = 2$	16.0923 ± 272.0470	17.1524 ± 202.1565	12.8318 ± 162.4850
$N = 4$	13.9292 ± 57.6704	4.8652 ± 39.4801	1.7012 ± 26.9667
$N = 6$	16.6490 ± 27.5010	4.2428 ± 16.8326	—————
$N = 8$	18.1471 ± 17.3227	4.8290 ± 9.4596	—————

Table 3: Average differences $|\alpha_R - \alpha_{R,\Delta d}|$ and their errors, for the case of plaquette diagonals, showing that the differences are compatible with zero. All numbers and errors reported are to be multiplied by 10^{-5} .

but in the case $d = 3$ as well. In all these spacetime dimensions the results indicate that we have $\lambda_R = 0$ on every finite N -lattice, and not only in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit. In the case $d = 3$ the dimensionfull coupling constant Λ_R can only be different from zero in the continuum limit if the dimensionless parameter λ_R goes to zero sufficiently slowly as $N \rightarrow \infty$. Instead of this, we find that our results are consistent with λ_R being zero on each finite lattice, thus implying that $\Lambda_R = 0$ as well. The first strong evidence of triviality is the fact that the momentum-space propagator of the non-linear theory matches so well the form of the momentum-space propagator of the free theory, with no more than the adjustment of just two parameters, the residue R and the renormalized mass parameter α_R , as shown in Equation (27).

Both the fact that the values of α_R from the momentum-space propagator and the fact that the values of $\alpha_{R,\Delta\ell}$ and $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$ from the local squared differences over links and plaquette diagonals match so well, in each separate case, the results from the free theory, as defined in Equations (27), (41) and (42), constitute strong evidence that the non-linear theory is trivial, since they show that its expectation values can be obtained from a related model with a Gaussian action. The fact that these two very different types of measurement, one in momentum space and the other two in position space, performed in the non-linear and hence non-Gaussian theory, give exactly the same result for the renormalized mass parameter α_R , is further evidence of this property. In addition to this, even in the case of the values of $\alpha_{R,s}$, $\alpha_{R,\ell}$ and $\alpha_{R,d}$, as defined in Equations (38), (39) and (40), although they do not match the corresponding values of α_R from momentum space so well, where they do match those results approximately they do so in a way that is clearly not related to the value of N . These mismatches can be understood completely in terms of the symmetry breaking mechanism and its effect on the zero mode, regardless of the value of N , and

independently of the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit.

One usually associates the phenomenon of triviality with the continuum limit, in the sense that it would become exactly valid only in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit. One would expect this phenomenon to be ultimately related to the central limit theorem of mathematical statistics. However, here we see that in some cases, at least, the relations implied by triviality come into force even before the continuum limit is taken. If we consider, as an example for the discussion, the matching of the results for α_R and for $\alpha_{R,\Delta\ell}$, if this match was a consequence of the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit, then one would naturally be led to try to detect deviations from that match by going to as small a lattice as possible. However, the smallest possible lattice in our case here is $N = 2$, and even in that case the match seems to be essentially perfect. The same can be said of the match of the results for α_R and for $\alpha_{R,\Delta d}$. In addition to this, it is clear that the excellent fit of the momentum-space propagator of the non-linear theory to the form of the propagator in the free theory also does not depend at all on the value of N . All this gives origin to a brand new mystery, about the root origin of these results, since this surprisingly precise match clearly cannot be explained in terms of the statistical properties of the system in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit. It seems to be a property of the statistical ensemble of the theory, the averages over which give the observables on finite lattices.

We may conclude that the dynamics of this theory can be described by the statement that the whole physical effect of the non-linear theory is to determine α_R from the free parameters (α, λ) , and to generate an expectation value v_R of the field, in terms of the free same parameters. The expectation value v_R is related to the first momentum of the statistical distribution, and the renormalized mass parameter α_R to the second momentum. Only these two momenta are in play in this theory, and no others seem to be relevant. Interestingly, these are exactly the two momenta that are relevant for the role that the scalar field theories play in the standard model of particle physics. But we can go beyond that, since it is very likely that the results shown here can be extended to the family of scalar field theories with non-linear terms given by $\lambda\varphi^{2p}$, with integer $p > 2$, and possibly to any stable potential $V(\varphi)$.

This exploration led us to introduce the various local observables that can be used for the determination of the renormalized mass parameter α_R , as given in Equations (38) through (42). These observables were revealed to be precise tools for the determination of this parameter, and ultimately for the determination of the renormalized mass. It is clear that these local observables for the renormalized mass parameter α_R can be very useful instruments. In fact, in any case in which we have any reason to introduce into the theory an external source that is dependent on position, and which is more than just an infinitesimal one meant at the taking of derivatives, they constitute the only reasonable way to measure the renormalized mass.

While only two of the five local observables defined here work with complete precision, this can be attributed to the symmetry breaking mechanism, and to the fact that in our simulations here the random drift of the direction of symmetry breaking makes unavailable to us the observables needed for the necessary subtractions of the other three local observables. It is to be expected that when an external source is present and the subtracted observables are used, at least four of the five observables defined here, those given in Equations (39) through (42), would be usable with the same high level of accuracy and precision. This would, of course, require the realization of whole new set of simulations, for example with the inclusion in the action of a constant external source.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no experimental datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study. Nevertheless, since the numerical simulation data used in this paper is rather extensive, and took almost half a million hours of CPU time to produce, the whole set of statistically processed data, as well as a fairly complete set of vector-formatted graphs, are available for download from Zenodo [7].

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors hereby certify that there are no actual or potential conflicts of interest of any of the authors in relation to this article.

A No Correlations in the Continuum Limit

Let us show that the dimensionless lattice fields at any two different lattice sites become completely uncorrelated from each other in the continuum limit. This will be based on the general properties that the dimensionfull two-point function is expected to have in the continuum limit, in any well-defined quantum field theory. Let us first consider the two-point function of the dimensionfull field in the continuum limit. Given our current circumstances here, in which we have $\langle \phi \rangle_N = 0$ and $\langle \tilde{\phi} \rangle_N = 0$, for simplicity we will use the non-subtracted expectation values of the fields, but the same argument can be repeated for the subtracted ones when it is the case to do so. In momentum space the two-point function is given by an expression such as

$$\left\langle \left| \tilde{\phi}(\vec{p}) \right|^2 \right\rangle = \frac{R(\vec{p})}{|\vec{p}|^2 + m_R^2}, \quad (76)$$

where \vec{p} is the four-momentum, while in position space we have

$$\left\langle \phi(\vec{x}_1) \phi(\vec{x}_2) \right\rangle = G_2(|\vec{x}_1 - \vec{x}_2|), \quad (77)$$

where G_2 is a two-point Green's function. This position-space two-point Green's function is related to the two-point correlation function between the corresponding dimensionless lattice fields, as we will discuss momentarily. The function G_2 above has the general property that in the continuum limit it diverges to infinity when $\vec{x}_1 \rightarrow \vec{x}_2$, and has finite and non-zero values for all $\vec{x}_1 \neq \vec{x}_2$. It is to be expected that this would be the case for any well-defined quantum field theory, since G_2 is a Green's function.

We can provide some illustrative examples of this using the free theory, where everything can be calculated in detail by analytic means. On finite lattices the squared dispersion of values $\sigma^2(N)$ of the field at any arbitrarily given site, which is defined in Equations (73) and (74), is a finite number, of course. In addition to this, in the cases $d \geq 3$ the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit of this quantity exists and is finite, of the order of 1, in fact. The values in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit can be obtained with good precision by adding up progressively larger finite sums and extrapolating to $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit, and are given approximately by the numbers shown in Equation (75). The Green's functions $G_2(|\vec{x}_1 - \vec{x}_2|)$ in the continuum limit are finite and non-zero away from the origin $|\vec{x}_1 - \vec{x}_2| = 0$. If $r = |\vec{x}_1 - \vec{x}_2|$ is the distance between the points \vec{x}_1 and \vec{x}_2 we have the exact results of the free theory, within a very large lattice box,

$$\begin{aligned}
d = 3: \quad G_2(r) &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{(2\pi r)} e^{-m_R r}, \\
d = 4: \quad G_2(r) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{m_R}{2\pi r} K_1(m_R r), \\
d = 5: \quad G_2(r) &= \pi \frac{1 + m_R r}{(2\pi r)^3} e^{-m_R r},
\end{aligned} \tag{78}$$

where K_n is the modified cylindrical Bessel function of the second kind and order n . The limits of these functions in the case in which the mass m_R goes to zero are given by an inverse-power decay with the distance, which depends on the spacetime dimension d ,

$$\begin{aligned}
d = 3: \quad \lim_{m_R \rightarrow 0} G_2(r) &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{(2\pi r)}, \\
d = 4: \quad \lim_{m_R \rightarrow 0} G_2(r) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi r)^2}, \\
d = 5: \quad \lim_{m_R \rightarrow 0} G_2(r) &= \pi \frac{1}{(2\pi r)^3}.
\end{aligned} \tag{79}$$

For finite and non-zero values of m_R and large values of r , with $r \gg 1/m_R$, the asymptotic behavior of these functions is given by an exponential decay with the distance,

$$\begin{aligned}
d = 3: \quad G_2(r) &\simeq \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{(2\pi r)} e^{-m_R r}, \\
d = 4: \quad G_2(r) &\simeq \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sqrt{m_R}}{(2\pi r)^{3/2}} e^{-m_R r}, \\
d = 5: \quad G_2(r) &\simeq \frac{1}{2} \frac{m_R}{(2\pi r)^2} e^{-m_R r}.
\end{aligned} \tag{80}$$

As one can see, all these functions diverge as an inverse power of r for $r \rightarrow 0$. Back to the general case, so long as the Green's function diverges at the origin, and since the relation between the dimensionless lattice field φ and the dimensionfull field ϕ is given by $\varphi = a^{(d-2)/2} \phi$, it follows that the corresponding relation between the lattice correlation function and the two-point function is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \varphi(\vec{n}_1) \varphi(\vec{n}_2) \rangle &= \langle \phi(\vec{x}_1) \phi(\vec{x}_2) \rangle a^{d-2} \\
&= G_2(r) a^{d-2}.
\end{aligned} \tag{81}$$

Since we know that for $d \geq 3$ the lattice correlation function on the left-hand side has a finite and non-zero value at $\vec{n}_1 = \vec{n}_2$ in the continuum limit, which is the result of the product of the factor $a^{d-2} \rightarrow 0$ with the divergence of the dimensionfull two-point Green's function $G_2(r)$ at the origin, it follows that at any other point, where the two-point function $G_2(r)$ is finite in the continuum limit, we must have that the lattice correlation function goes to zero as a^{d-2} , where $d \geq 3$. Therefore the dimensionless lattice fields at two different sites become completely uncorrelated to each other in the continuum limit.

B Divergence of the Perturbative Series

Here we will prove, by “reductio ad absurdum”, that the perturbative series of the $\lambda \phi_d^{2p}$ scalar polynomial theory defined on the Euclidean lattice, with any even integer power $2p$

with $p \geq 2$, is necessarily divergent for all values of λ except for the reference point $\lambda_0 = 0$ of the series, for all spacetime dimensions $d \geq 3$, and for all lattice sizes $N \geq 2$, all the way to the $N \rightarrow \infty$ continuum limit. What is meant here by divergence is simply the lack of convergence, in the usual sense used in the theory of analytic functions.

B.1 Definition of the Theory

The definition that we will adopt here for the scalar field theories is the one discussed in detail in Subsection 2.1, obtained from their realization on the Euclidean lattice, in $d \geq 3$ spacetime dimensions, for all even integer powers $2p$ with $p \geq 2$, and any finite value of the lattice size $N \geq 2$. The action of the theory in terms of these parameters is given, for the case $p = 2$, in Equation (4), and can be simply generalized to $2p$ instead of 4. The expectation values of the observables $\mathcal{O}_N[\varphi]$ are defined by the ratios of N^d -dimensional multiple integrals shown in Equation (7), again generalized to the power $2p$. The continuum theory in Minkowski space is obtained in the $N \rightarrow \infty$ limit, when we make a Wick rotation from the resulting Euclidean space to the corresponding Minkowski space. If there is a perturbative series for this observable, developed around the exactly solvable case of the free theory for $\lambda = 0$, then it must be given by the expression shown in Equation (24), which is a real power series on λ , developed around the reference point $\lambda = 0$. It is important to recall that, as was shown before in Subsection 2.2, the theory does not exist at all for $\lambda < 0$, a fact that can be easily generalized to the case of the power $2p$.

B.2 Analytic Functions and Power Series

Since the perturbative series shown in Equation (24) is a power series on λ , we may extend it to complex values of λ , and then use the power-series theorems that can be established in the theory of complex analytic functions in order to establish some facts about it. After this is done we may reduce the series back to the real case, in which all the facts established in the complex case continue to be equally valid in their corresponding real forms. We will use the following mathematical facts from the theory of analytic functions, which are all rather basic theorems that can be found in any text on that theory [8], and that we will quickly review here. Given a complex power series around a point z_0 of the complex plane, which we denote here as

$$f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n (z - z_0)^n, \quad (82)$$

which presumably is some function of z , so long as the series is convergent, and where $\{a_n, n = 0, \dots, \infty\}$ is some arbitrary set of finite complex coefficients, which for the time being remain unspecified, the following set of mathematical facts holds.

1. The series is trivially convergent at the point $z = z_0$, since in this case it reduces to a single term, $f(z_0) = a_0$.
2. If the coefficients a_n are such that a second point $z_1 \neq z_0$ exists in the complex plane, such that the series is convergent at z_1 , then it follows that the series is absolutely convergent in the strict interior of a disc in the complex plane, which is centered at z_0 and has radius given by $\rho_1 = |z_1 - z_0|$.
3. Since absolute convergence implies, in particular, plain point-wise convergence, it then follows that the series is convergent in that open disc.

4. The series is also uniformly convergent within any closed set contained strictly within that open disc, and therefore can be term-wise integrated and differentiated.
5. Within that open disk the series converges to an analytic function $f(z)$, that satisfies the Cauchy-Riemann conditions.
6. Where it converges the power series is identical to the Taylor series of the analytic function $f(z)$, written around the reference point z_0 .
7. If that analytic function $f(z)$, when maximally extended to the complex plane, has a singularity of any type at some point outside the open disk of radius ρ_1 , then there is a maximal disc of convergence of the power series. The radius of the maximal disc of convergence is known as the *convergence radius* ρ_c , and is given by the distance from the reference point z_0 to the singular point of the analytic function $f(z)$ which is closer to z_0 . That singularity of $f(z)$ is therefore located at the rim of the maximal disc of convergence.
8. With the use of the facts given in items 2, 3 and 5, it can now be shown by “reductio ad absurdum” that at any point strictly outside the maximal disc of convergence the series is necessarily divergent. This is simply done, since the analytic function $f(z)$ has a singularity at some point on the rim of the maximal disc of convergence, so that if there is a point outside that disc where the series converges, then it follows from items 2, 3 and 5 above that the series converges to an analytic function at that singular point, which is absurd. Therefore the series diverges everywhere strictly outside the maximal disc of convergence.

A completely divergent series is one for which the convergence radius ρ_c is zero. Such a series diverges everywhere except at the reference point z_0 . It should be noted here that strictly outside its maximal convergence disk a power series diverges to infinity very fast.

B.3 Application of the Analytic Results

Let us now apply these results to our case here, with $\lambda_0 = z_0$. Given an observable $\mathcal{O}_N[\varphi]$, the series shown in Equation (24) is clearly convergent at $\lambda_0 = 0$, where the theory reduces to the free theory. Let us now assume that there is a point $\lambda_1 > 0$ for which the series converges. Extending the series to the complex λ plane we conclude that there must be a disc around $\lambda_0 = 0$, with non-zero radius, within which the series converges. This disc includes the segment $(-\lambda_1, \lambda_1)$ of the real λ axis.

Since this disc includes negative real values of λ , we therefore conclude that the series converges at points where the theory does not exist at all, which is absurd. Therefore, we conclude that λ_1 must be outside the maximal disc of convergence of the series, and hence the radius of convergence ρ_c must be smaller than λ_1 ,

$$\rho_c < \lambda_1. \tag{83}$$

Since this is true for all strictly positive real values of λ_1 , no matter how small, we conclude that we must have

$$\rho_c = 0. \tag{84}$$

In other words, the perturbative series must be completely divergent, that is, divergent everywhere but at the reference point $\lambda_0 = 0$, for any observable $\mathcal{O}_N[\varphi]$, for all finite values

of the lattice size N , and for any spacetime dimension $d \geq 3$. Of course, this then implies that the same is true in any continuum limit, in which we necessarily have that $N \rightarrow \infty$.

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